

APPLICATION OF COMPLEX COMPOUNDS IN MEDICINE

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Аннотация. Роль комплексных соединений в жизнедеятельности живых организмов огромна. Организм представляет систему, состоящую из множества комплексообразователей и лигандов, с определенным соотношением между ними. Нарушение баланса компонентов (металло-лигандного гомеостаза) приводит к развитию патологических состояний. В процессах обмена веществ фундаментальную роль играет биокатализ, в котором принимают участие металлоферменты. Ферменты, которые содержат в своем составе ионы металла или которые ими активируются, называют металлоферментами. Это достаточно распространенная группа биологических катализаторов, в которых ионы металлов могут выполнять роль как активатора, так и кофактора.

Abstract. The role of complex compounds in the vital activity of living organisms is enormous. The organism is a system consisting of many complexing agents and ligands, with a certain ratio between them. Violation of the balance of components (metal-ligand homeostasis) leads to the development of pathological conditions. Biocatalysis, in which metalloenzymes participate, plays a fundamental role in metabolic processes. Enzymes that contain metal ions or that are activated by them are called metalloenzymes. This is a fairly common group of biological catalysts in which metal ions can act as both an activator and a cofactor.

Annotatsiya. Tirik organizmlar hayotida kompleks birikmalarning roli juda katta. Organizm ko'plab kompleks hosil qiluvchi moddalar va ligandlardan tashkil topgan tizimni ifodalaydi, ular orasida ma'lum nisbat mavjud. Komponentlarning nomutanosibliigi (metall-ligand gomeostazi) patologik sharoitlarning rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Metallofermentlar ishtirok etadigan biokataliz metabolik jarayonlarda asosiy rol o'ynaydi. Tarkibida metall ionlari bo'lgan yoki ular tomonidan faollashtirilgan fermentlar metallofermentlar deyiladi. Bu juda keng tarqalgan biologik katalizatorlar guruhi bo'lib, unda metall ionlari ham faollashtiruvchi, ham kofaktor sifatida harakat qilishi mumkin.

Relevance. Complex compounds are widely used in medicine and have the following important values in the body and in analytical chemistry:

- complex molecules of hemoglobin and chlorophyll are complex compounds;
- complex compounds are molecules of many enzymes;
- complex compounds are used in medicine as medicinal preparations;
- chelate compounds of complexone III with various metals have acquired great importance for analytical chemistry.

Materials and methods.

Hemoglobin, chlorophyll and their functions

Hemoglobin and chlorophyll are complex compounds of iron and magnesium, respectively.

Hemoglobin is a molecule consisting of the protein globin (2 α - and 2 β -chains) and 4 pigment groups (heme), which are capable of reversibly binding molecular oxygen. An erythrocyte contains an average of 400 million hemoglobin molecules.

The main function of hemoglobin is to transport oxygen and carbon dioxide. In addition, hemoglobin has buffering properties, as well as the ability to bind toxic substances. In humans, in the capillaries of the lungs, under conditions of excess oxygen, the latter combines with hemoglobin. The blood flow delivers erythrocytes containing hemoglobin molecules with bound oxygen to organs and tissues where there is little oxygen; here, the oxygen necessary for the oxidative processes is released from its bond with hemoglobin.

Chlorophyll is a green pigment that colors plant chloroplasts green. It is involved in photosynthesis. The main source of energy for life is sunlight, which is absorbed by chlorophyll, a magnesium complex with macrocyclic ligands. The color of the foliage of photosynthetic plants is due to the high concentration of chlorophyll. During photosynthesis, the chlorophyll molecule undergoes changes, absorbing light energy, which is then used in the photochemical reaction of carbon dioxide and water to form organic matter (usually carbohydrates).

Vitamin B12

The B12 (cobalamin) family of vitamins is a complex compound that includes porphyrin derivatives of cobalt, in which the complexing ion Co^{2+} is bound to five nitrogen atoms of the chelating ligand and one monodentate ligand-cyano group CN^- , anion OH^- group. The therapeutic effect of cobalamins is practically independent of the nature of the monodentate ligand, because in the human body they all quickly turn into cyanocobalamin. Vitamins of the B12 family have a wide range of biological effects. They participate in the catabolism of fats and proteins, the synthesis of methionine and hematopoiesis processes. Vitamin B12 deficiency leads to the development of anemia and degeneration of nerve tissue. With a vitamin B12 deficiency against the background of anemic clinical picture or without it, neurological disorders may occur, including demyelination and irreversible death of nerve cells. Symptoms of such pathology are numbness or tingling of the limbs and ataxia. Vitamin B12 deficiency affects the occurrence of clinical depression in elderly patients.

Complex compounds in the body

The role of complex compounds in the vital activity of living organisms is enormous. The organism is a system consisting of many complexing agents and ligands, with a certain ratio between them. Violation of the balance of components (metal-ligand homeostasis) leads to the development of pathological conditions. Biocatalysis, in which metalloenzymes participate, plays a fundamental role in metabolic processes. Enzymes that contain metal ions or that are activated by them are called metalloenzymes. This is a fairly common group of biological catalysts, in which metal ions Fe, Co, Mn, Zn, Mg, Cu can act as both an activator and a cofactor.

In total, about 700 enzymes are known, a quarter of which are metalloenzymes. They mainly contain transition metal ions (iron is included in 70 enzymes, copper - 30, manganese - 12). Enzymes are unique catalysts with unrivaled efficiency and high selectivity. Biocatalytic reactions that occur in the body with the participation of metalloenzymes are divided into oxidation-reduction and hydrolytic. Transition metal ions act as cofactors in oxidation-reduction reactions. The main oxidizer in biological processes is molecular oxygen of the atmosphere or water. The main oxidation products are water and carbon dioxide. A large group of metalloenzymes is known - dehydrogenases (with zinc in the active center), catalyzing reactions of hydride ion splitting from various substrates, for example, alcohol dehydrogenases split

hydride ions from alcohols, converting them into aldehydes. The oxidation reactions of aldehydes to carboxylic acids are catalyzed by aldehyde oxidases containing molybdenum.

In hydrolytic reactions, electrons are not transferred, but only chemical bonds are broken and formed in various substrates. For example, zinc carbonic anhydrase catalyzes the process of converting carbon dioxide into hydrocarbonate ion. Hydrolysis of the peptide bond of the N- and C-terminal sections occurs under the action of aminopeptidase with magnesium, zinc or manganese in the active center and carboxypeptidase with zinc in the active center. Non-specific hydrolysis of the polypeptide bond at any section is catalyzed by calcium-containing protease.

Complex compounds of bioligands with bioactive metals as medicinal preparations

Currently, the drug Cisplatin, which is a complex compound of platinum [Pt (NH₃)₂Cl₂], is widely used in medical practice. Cisplatin has pronounced cytotoxic, bactericidal and mutagenic properties. The basis of the biological properties is the ability of the compound to penetrate the cell nucleus with the formation of a stable complex with DNA, which prevents DNA replication, i.e. DNA synthesis is inhibited and cell division stops. This platinum complex is currently widely used in medicine as an anticancer agent.

The drug *Kobavit* is a complex compound of vitamin U with cobalt Co³⁺. Kobavit has a pronounced hepatoprotective, antianemic and antiulcer activity. As a hepatoprotector, Kobavit is used in acute, protracted and chronic forms of hepatitis, liver cirrhosis, etc. The use of Kobavit in acute forms of viral hepatitis prevents the development of chronic forms of the disease, and in chronic forms - prevents further progression of the pathological process, including the development of liver cirrhosis. Kobavit has a high antianemic effect in the treatment of anemia of various etiologies and varying degrees of severity.

The drug *Cupir* is a complex compound of pyridoxine with copper Cu²⁺. Cupir affects the intensity of metabolic processes, has antitoxic properties, increases the production of melanin. It is used in the treatment of vitiligo.

The drug *Cobalt 30* is a complex compound of methionine with cobalt Co³⁺. It has an effect of ionizing radiation with accompanying disorders of hematopoiesis (the process of hematopoiesis) and leukopenia. Under the influence of the drug Cobalt-30, the content of band leukocytes increases. Cobalt 30 is easily tolerated by patients and has no side effects. The drug is used in the clinic to treat leukopenia.

Feramide is a complex compound of iron Fe²⁺ with nicotinamide. Feramide restores iron deficiency in the body, stimulates erythropoiesis. It helps eliminate laboratory and clinical signs of anemia. Feramide is widely used in the treatment of posthemorrhagic anemia, iron deficiency anemia of various origins.

The drug *Coamide* is a complex compound of cobalt Co²⁺ with nicotinamide. Coamide is a stimulator of hematopoiesis, promotes the absorption of iron by the body and stimulates the processes of its transformation (formation of protein complexes, synthesis of hemoglobin), normalizes erythropoietic activity and eliminates anemia. It is used in the treatment of hypochromic and hypoplastic anemia (in iron deficiency anemia simultaneously with iron preparations). From the above it is clear that complex compounds of biometals with biologically active ligands are more active, compared to inorganic salts of biometals.

Application of complex compounds in quantitative analysis methods

Complexometry methods were widely used after the discovery of organic substances belonging to the class of aminocarboxylic acids, which turned out to be excellent complexing agents. These compounds were called complexones, and the methods of volumetric analysis

based on their application were called complexometry. The best known complexones include: - nitrilotriacetic acid (complexone 1), ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (complexone II), disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA, complex III, trilon B). In practice, the well-soluble disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (trilon B) is usually used. The anion of this salt forms particularly strong five-membered cycles with metal ions and can act as a tetra-, penta- and hexadentate ligand. Currently, complexometric methods for determining more than 80 chemical elements have been developed. Complexometry has become widespread in medical and biological research. This method is necessary for the quantitative determination of calcium, magnesium and many microelements in living organisms. Complexometry is used in the analysis of medicinal raw materials, drinking, mineral and waste water. In biology and medicine, complexones are used not only for analytical purposes, but also as stabilizers in blood storage, since complexones bind metal ions that catalyze oxidation reactions.

Conclusions. As can be seen from the above, complex compounds are widely used in medicine.

REFERENCES

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